

DEVELOPMENT OF CONNECTED SPEECH OF STUDENTS WITH MENTAL DISABILITY BASED ON THE USE OF FAIRY TALE THERAPY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10432754>

Abstract: In this article, based on the use of fairy tale therapy, there are opinions about the pedagogical conditions for the development of connected speech in children with mental retardation. Also, the possibilities of fairy tale therapy to shape the abilities of students are described.

Key words: Educational system, fairy tale therapy, mentally retarded student, special education, pedagogical conditions.

Introduction:

It is the period when the first ideas about life are formed for a mentally retarded child. Any knowledge acquired during this period is of great importance in the child's learning of other subjects. That is why today attention is being paid to the preschool education system. It is emphasized that education of the future generation should start from preschool age. It is also worth saying that it is necessary to start raising a child not only from the pre-school age, but also from the mother's womb. Because the child begins to perceive the world from the moment he is in his mother's womb. Every parent should pay attention to this. In order to raise a perfect generation, first of all, parents themselves should be spiritual. For this reason, if today's young people get a good education and have a wide world development, the next generation will become highly spiritual. That is why the President is creating sufficient conditions not only for the pre-school education system, but also for young people to get an education and, if necessary, improve their knowledge in foreign countries.

Fairy tales are considered one of the most convenient and effective ways to promote good human qualities or, on the contrary, describe bad aspects of character, helping children to distinguish between good and bad and to understand life in children's language. Although fairy tales are not true, they are considered to be one of the most effective ways of teaching that have a positive effect on children. Fairy tales provide basic knowledge for children's development in an interesting and simple way. Also, fairy tales are one of the main factors in developing children's logical thinking in order to expand their thinking and strengthen their memory. The plot is based on various adventure events, instills goodness and human qualities, has the characteristic of being quickly preserved in memory, and the fairy tales, which are easy to tell, easy to pronounce, and consist of various puzzles, have a positive effect on the upbringing of children. shows. Mental development of children between three and seven years of age, formation of thinking is the main task. This is done with the help of fairy tales.

A fairy tale is a system of symbols, with the help of which a child interprets the surrounding reality as he understands it. When choosing a fairy tale, it is necessary to take into account the age and spiritual development of children. Fairy tales can benefit children

only if the teacher and parents pay attention to this. The use of fairy tales has a positive effect on the development of children's abilities. Using fairy tales, it is possible to achieve high results in teaching children. Fairy tale therapy is also used when working with children. Fairytale therapy is the oldest method. Our ancestors did not rush to punish a criminal child while raising children, but told him a fairy tale, through which the children understood their mistakes. Fairy tales served as a means of moral education and taught children how to live. It is possible to help a child's development a lot if every parent and teacher knows how a fairy tale affects a person's life. As a result of fairy tale therapy, the child feels the support of adults. Also, by perceiving the world of fairy tales, it is possible to create the necessary conditions for the development of the emotional sphere of a preschool child, to enrich it with images and ideas that shape the imagination.

The methods of fairy tale therapy should be mastered by parents. For this, they should receive advice from educators and psychologists. Types of fairy tales used by fairy tale therapists:

1) Meditative (used to get rid of psycho-emotional stress). As a rule, there are no negative characters and conflicts in the plot of mediated fairy tales.

2) Didactic, in the form of an educational task. It is used to convey new knowledge to children.

3) Artistic (people). They have folk wisdom. A simple, understandable plot contributes to moral education.

4) Psychotherapeutic. A special feature of these fairy tales is a happy ending. Children draw pictures for them, put on plays, make toys based on the images of the main characters.

5) Psychocorrective. Told fairy tales have a soft and indifferent effect on the behavior of a preschool child. The moral of the story is not discussed, it gives the child the opportunity to think alone.

Mathematical tales are used to educate children and develop their minds. A mathematical fairy tale is a fictional text based on the adventure genre. Mathematical stories help children develop logical thinking. How to develop mathematical abilities and interest in mathematics in preschool children through fairy tales. When using fairy tales in the process of forming elementary mathematical ideas in mentally retarded children, the main attention is paid to its deep understanding, conscious and active assimilation. It should be noted that the regular use of specially selected repertoires of oral tales in the group for the development of mathematical abilities is aimed at developing cognitive abilities and abilities, expands the mathematical outlook of preschool children, promotes mathematical development, improves the quality of mathematical training, provides children with more opportunities.

The following fairy tale can be cited as an example of mathematical fairy tales that help children's mental development: "Who likes the number 2?" a fairy tale. Number 2 was walking down the road and heard someone crying under a bush. - I - I - I'm lost. -He looked under the bush and saw a big gray chick there. - Who is your mother? - My mother is a beautiful and big bird. "He looks like you," chirped the chick. Don't cry, we will find him, said number 2. - He put the chick on its tail and they went to look for its mother. Soon, the Two saw a beautiful bird with a long tail in the meadow. - Isn't this your child, beautiful bird? asked number 2. - I'm not a bird, I'm a snake. I don't even have wings. "Pee-pee, this is not my mother, my mother is like you," said the chick. The two of them walked a long way, and then they saw how a big bird had landed in a big square. - Have you lost your cock, big bird? - asked number 2 politely. "I'm not

a bird, I'm an airplane." Airplanes don't have chicks, replied the airplane. Suddenly, number 2 saw a big snow-white bird falling from the sky. "My swan, I was looking for you," the bird hummed. "Hey, meet number 2. He saved me," cried the chick. - Thank you for your help. You are very kind and like a swan. "Let's be friends"¹. Such fairy tales develop children's mental abilities. Educators, in cooperation with parents, should tell children more such fairy tales and discuss them through questions. Only then will the lessons become stronger in the children's memory.

Today, the number of parents who read fairy tales to boas is unfortunately decreasing. Along with the intellectual education of children, it is possible to influence the moral education of children through Uzbek folk tales and educate them correctly. For this, educators should give advice to parents in this regard and recommend fairy-tale books themselves. Because the teacher knows the fairy tales suitable for the child's age and can recommend the right book. In addition, modern technologies are developing more and more. It is not wrong to say that this development has had its effect on the education system and has increased the effectiveness of education to a certain level. Multimedia tools made it possible for children to listen to fairy tales. In addition, turning fairy tales into cartoons is very interesting and educational for children. But it is not recommended to get attached to this process. Because the fact that parents read fairy tales to children themselves affects the child's psyche and forms a feeling of love in them. Every parent should take this into consideration.

It would be appropriate if educators would give their recommendations in this regard during conversations and meetings with parents, and conduct trainings for the formation of pedagogical skills of parents. Also, using the same fairy tales all the time in the educational process does not give the expected result, it is necessary to always use new fairy tales. In such conditions, new knowledge is connected to each other. In conclusion, children's knowledge can be further improved through fairy tales. Fairy tales are important in the development of children, especially in their mental and moral development. In addition, it is necessary to take into account that fairy tales expand the scope of children's thinking and strengthen their memory, and choose fairy tales for children based on their interest. In addition, the effectiveness of education will increase if the educator uses his pedagogical skills to adapt the characters of fairy tales to the child's interest and use them in the educational process.

¹ Лопатина А., Скребцова М. Сказочная математика. М.: Амрита-Русь, 2009.-9б 765

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